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Mobility Programme

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1. Introduction

Learning is at the heart of the COEVOLVERS project aiming at introducing new concepts and approaches for nature-based solutions to better take into account the vulnerable people and non-humans – including animals and plants – in new forms of NBS governance, models and tools. The learning is enabled through a transdisciplinary interaction between various people, researchers, stakeholders from different sectors by offering a unique opportunity for individual stakeholders or researchers, society and sectors (Barth & Michelsen, 2013; Pohl et al. 2021). We anticipate that learning through collaboration and situated experiences across COEVOLVERS Living Labs would enhance and trigger our creativity and visionary ideas and strategies, stakeholder participation and institutional arrangements of NBS design and implementation (Wickenberg et al. 2022). Moreover, perceiving and engaging with others may lead to reassessment of inherent biases and promoting transformation of beliefs and worldviews at the individual or collective level (Hepple et al. 2017), which is necessary when responding to the global social and ecological challenges (Halford 2023). Therefore, our learning framework is related to transformative learning.

Transformative learning in the COEVOLVERS project is enhanced by various learning spaces, processes and methods (Fig. 2) including a Mobility Programme. The Mobility Programme enables mobility between project partners and especially between the Living Lab partners thereby fostering learning between the respective mobility parties, but also across the project. This document introduces the purpose and procedures of the COEVOLVERS Mobility Programme. The Mobility Programme defines the purpose and procedures to make the mobility effective and useful for the individuals, partner organizations and the project overall. First, we briefly discuss transformative learning as an overarching approach in the context of transdisciplinary and transformative research (section 2) and see how the idea of transformative learning can be embedded within COEVOLVERS Mobility Programme. We then outline how this is applied in COEVOLVERS and its transformative learning spaces (section 3). In section 4, we describe the purpose of the Mobility of programme, possible learning topics and its implementation. This document is a so-called “living document”, which will be updated with reports (templates for reflections, Annex 2) and learning diaries from the mobility activities. Based on these assessments and a summary of the Mobility activities will be provided at the end of the project. The final reflection of the outcomes of the learning will be summarised at the end of the project (Section 5). The document is part of Task 1.4. (Learning within and across LLs, and with Overseas Cousins).

2. Transformative learning as an overarching framework for the learning in COEVOLVERS

There are a number of learning theories mostly developed in and by educational sciences to support pedagogy in formal learning environments, usually focusing on individual learning with an emphasis on competences, learning objectives and outcomes. Yet, sustainability transition and transformation call for other approaches for learning in informal contexts to enhance change including transformative learning (Singer-Brodowski 2023).

Transformative learning has been defined as "learning that changes problematic frames of reference—sets of fixed assumptions and expectations (habits of mind, meaning perspectives, mindsets)—to make them more inclusive, discriminating, open, reflective, and emotionally able to change" (Mezirow, 2003, p. 58). This implies that people shape their own understanding and interaction with their environments based on their unique perspectives, habits, and beliefs. Transformative learning then becomes a journey of scrutinising, challenging, and adapting these perceptions. The journey starts with questioning these references and perspectives through reflection and reflexivity, which may gradually change the meaning perspectives and develop a more inclusive, critical, open and reflective perspective on the issue concerned, and continuously cultivate a deeper level of critical thinking. To effectively engage in this learning trajectory, learners must exhibit qualities like emotional depth and self-creation (Mezirow, 2000). Kear (2013) further distilled this process (Figure 1.) into three primary phases of the transformative learning theory and introduced a model using the narrative inquiry method, which considers assessment factors like human interaction, multi-faceted learning, intertwined experiences, and experiential learning.

Figure 1. Transformative learning model showing key elements to assess, adapted from Mezirow, 2000 and Kear, 2013.

Transformative learning is assumed to take place in less-organized informal settings and through practices. This holds that learning processes can be facilitated by creating certain learning conditions instead of trying to steer the processes themselves. Here we focus on the key prerequisites of such conditions in a context of transdisciplinary research process: learning in real-life situations and reflection as a means to support and assess learning.

Transdisciplinary research aims to solve real life challenges. COEVOLVERS is about understanding how socio-politics could affect the design and implementation of the NBS in different contexts. This means that the context of the research can be considered as a problem space, as a platform, where learning may take place. Learning with a group of people, a kind of community of practice, interacting in a certain social and ecological setting with a variety of experiences and knowledge drawn from different practices, institutions, and societal domains foster knowledge creation and sharing in a specific domain of interest.

This diversity generates opportunities for reflection upon different theoretical and methodological perspectives, backgrounds and worldviews guiding the practice of the group. Reflection is learning and developing through examining the events or situation in-depth outside of oneself to work out for example what happened, what they thought or felt about it, why, who was involved and when, and what the others might have experienced and thought and felt about it. It is looking at the whole situation from as many angles as possible to make situations and people more comprehensible. This involves reviewing or reliving the experience to bring it into focus.

Storytelling approach, is a way of making meaning of experiences in all cultures and across all times, and it has been becoming popular means to further explore and assess transformative learning (Kroth & Cranton, 2014). Kier (2013) utilized a storytelling approach using key steps: Describing one's learning experience in a specific environment or during an activity; identifying factors that enhanced learning throughout the activities; and reflecting on any events or situations during the activities that significantly altered one's perspective or life. Using a narrative-based method (storytelling), transformative learning (Fig 1.) can be analysed by evaluating the learners' reports on the critical thinking and discussions that helped them make sense of the situation, reflecting on the assumptions and interpretations made during the process, and understanding how meaning-making was shaped through deliberations with peers.

3. Mobility Programme as part of transformative learning spaces in the COEVOLVERS project

In order to support our learning in the COEVOLVERS project we have established three interconnected learning spaces within the project (Figure 2.). The Monitoring Programme relates particularly to learning across the Living labs and consortium partners. First, COEVOLVERS **Living Labs** are kind of communities of practice (CoP), where learning takes place both individually and collectively (collaboratively), between the research teams, core groups and participants in various events, workshops, etc. The participating individuals represent different types of knowledge and practices and learning is about continuous testing and development of diversified tools and methods to support NBS implementation in the Living Lab context and contributing to the learning in the other spaces. Secondly, we systematically enhance learning between the researchers and disciplines **across the consortium**. This takes place more at the level of concepts and theories, facilitated through close dialogue and interactions between the practices and lessons learnt from Living Labs and through **the Mobility programme**. We have also established other platforms for facilitating such discussions, including regular Living Lab meetings, where Living Lab teams come together and exchange practical experiences (WP1) and Readers' Teatime for conceptual and theoretical discussions (WP2). Thirdly, we have connections **beyond the consortium and Living Labs** to other knowledge providers, like National Consultation Groups established in the WP5 (Task 5.1.), Overseas Cousins and two Horizon Europe Sibling projects, TRANS-lighthouses and Naturescapes, and other EU-projects and the Network Nature + community and the related Task Forces broadening the learning across different spatial and cultural contexts. National Consultation Groups established in WP5 (Task 5.1) also contribute to the learning by identifying the knowledge gaps and needs at regional and national level and addressing the needs and (up)scaling the solutions across Europe.

Individual researchers, experts, practitioners and participants are key mediators in these processes having multiple roles and contributing to collective learning. The learning takes place through interactions (i.e., face-to-face, online, and hybrid) and in different domain of interest (i.e., digital and social-media platform). All these learning spaces are bridging various boundaries that have been seen as necessary for transformative learning: cultural, spatial, temporal, and disciplinary boundaries (Wals, 2011).

Figure 2. Learning spaces in COEVOLVERS.

4. Purpose and focus of the Mobility Programme

COEVOLVERS Mobility Programme is designed to support mutual learning across the Living Labs but also between other project partners contributing to the learning at the project level. The programme may cultivate intercultural capacities, cross-fertilize knowledge and skills developed through collaborations and experiences. When aptly tailored, the Mobility Programme can also enhance intellectual adaptability by offering experiential learning opportunities in varied geo-political contexts and harmonise differences in experiences, interests, and values associated with NBS that arise from diverse settings.

The learning may focus for example on the following themes:

- the socio-political and ecological context of the Living Labs and NBS design, implementation and governance;
- methods: Living Lab teams possess different types of methodological and theoretical expertise. This calls for learning to apply these methods in different contexts thereby enhancing overall learning of the methods. This may cover both the co-creation methods (especially digital and art-based methods), but also the research methods developed and applied by Work Packages;
- stakeholder engagement and interaction: potential challenges related to the stakeholder engagement and ways to address them?
- means to understand and engage non-human animals
- bridging theories and practices: theories are needed to develop practices, practices in turn inform the development of the theories further.
- language and communication: Here the focus is on how to translate the knowledge and communicate about NBS, non-human animals, co-evolutionary thinking within and between different knowledge holders, researchers, practitioners and decision making more effectively.

Possible activities that may enhance learning during the mobility:

- Participating in Living Lab activities
- Experimenting/testing new methods, skills, concepts
- Writing joint papers
- Seminars, webinars, workshops, etc.

Funding and participants

- The Mobility programme is addressed especially to Living Labs, Living Lab researchers and experts. Each of the COEVOLVERS Living Lab partners (name the partners) have a dedicated budget for the Mobility Programme in their travel budget (3000 €). Funding will cover only travel costs (travels, accommodation and daily allowances).
- Also Living Lab participants, for example the key stakeholders active in the Labs, may be eligible for Mobility funding. Their costs as well as possible invited

visitors will be reported in Other goods, works and services category. The decisions of using the Mobility programme for different visits are made by the individual Living Lab team.

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5. Implementation of the Mobility programme

Implementation of the Mobility Plan includes the following phases (Figure 3.):

Figure 3. Implementation framework for Mobility programme in Coevolvers.

I. Initiating: Preparing for the mobility

The first phase includes various preparatory activities such as:

- discussing the needs of learning within a LL/WP
- identifying and contacting the possible LLs to visit
- elaborating about the mutual interests for the visit
- informing about your plans in the NextCloud ([link to excel](#))

II. Planning:

In the planning phase more detailed plans between the mobility parties will be made:

- mapping the needs and priorities between the host LL/WP and the visiting LL/WP towards the objectives which may be addressed or challenged during the visit
- identifying the possible added values of the visit for the visiting LL/WP, hosting LL/WP, the project, and the individual visitor
- defining the aims and potential programme and activities of the visit
- making a budget and travel plans
- developing a reasonable and realistic timetable allowing the set goals to be achieved and connecting the plans with the ongoing activities in the hosting LL
- conclude an agreement between the host and visiting individual/ organization (Annex 2)

III.Executing: Visiting, Collaborating and Learning

This is the phase of implementing the planned mobility between the parties.

- documenting systematically the context (social and environmental), activities (what was done and how) and reflections (how did it go and what did you learn) by means of, for example, notes, diary, recordings, photographs, videos, etc.
 - You may use the storytelling approach for reflecting during the visit and the events you participate in by
 - Describing learning experience in a specific environment or during an activity
 - Identifying factors that enhanced learning throughout the activities
 - Reflecting on any situations during the activities that significantly altered your perspective or life
- following the local ethical procedures and guidelines for your activities

IV.Reflecting and reporting

This phase consists of two types of reflections: individual and joint between the host and the visitor (templates for reflections, Annex 2).

a) Individual reflections

In the first phase each of the key participants of the mobility (at least the visitor and the host/hosts) reflect first individually the mobility from the learning point of view using a template (Annex 2, Section 1). Here the notes/diary, recordings, photos, videos, etc. collected during the visit can be used. Conducting individual reflections is a “pre-task” for preparing the joint reflections (see below). The individual reflections (i.e., the templates: Annex 2, Section 2) will not be included in the reports attached to this Mobility Programme.

b) Joint reflections

In the next phase the visitor reflects together with the host(s) on the same questions as a dialogue (Annex 2, Section 2). The joint reflection template will be attached to this Mobility Programme (see Section V).

V. Disseminating and submitting

In this phase, the visitor compiles the report consisting of the following elements:

1. Information of the mobility parties
2. Time and place of the mobility
3. Topic and objectives of the mobility, anticipated impact (based on Annex 1)
4. Programme of the mobility (on daily basis)
5. Joint reflection template (Annex 2, Section 2).

Please also attach photos, maps, etc. and other materials relevant to mobility. The report will be added as an annex to this document (Annex 3).

6. Finalisation of the Mobility programme

WP1 compiles all the mobility reports in Annex 3 and prepares a summary of the main lessons learnt and the benefits of the mobilities. The final mobility programme will be submitted no later than in month 45.

Literature

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Annex 1: Mobility agreement form (non-binding)

To be filled in by both parties prior to the mobility.

MOBILITY FOR RESEARCH AND TRAINING PURPOSES WITHIN COEVOLVERS

Mobility agreement between applying organization..... and receiving organization....., in order to participate in the Coevolvers* project Mobility programme and participant training and learning as part of exchange.

*COEVOLVERS – Coevolutionary approach to unlock the transformative potential of nature-based solutions for a more inclusive and resilient community. This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Framework Programme for Research and Innovation under Grant Agreement No.101084220.

Planned period of the research and training activity: from [00/00/2024] till [00/00/2024]
 Duration (days) – excluding travel days:xxx.....

Visitor

Name of the visitor(s)	
Gender, nationality	
Name of the organization, department, unit, address	
Role in the project	

Host

Name of the hosting researcher	
Gender, nationality	
Name of the organization, department, unit, address	
Role in the project	

I. PROPOSED MOBILITY

Overall purpose of the mobility: Describe the overall objective/topic of the mobility shortly.
Specific objectives and expectations of the mobility: Think for example of new understanding knowledge, specific skills or practices you like to deepen your understanding/solve your problem or any other etc. Visitor: Host:
Anticipated added values/impact of the mobility: You may describe these from the point of for visitor/visiting LL; host/hosting LLs; a common goal; project (which WP/Task it is linked to); personal 1) visitor/visiting LL 2) Host/hosting LL: 3) COEVOLVERS project (WP/Task) 4) personal 5) other
Activities to be carried out (tentative, for example participation/organising an event, writing together etc.):

II. COMMITMENT OF THE PARTIES

By signing this document, the visitor and host confirm that they approve the proposed mobility agreement and that they will share their experience during the visit as a source of inspiration to others.

The visiting researcher Name: Signature: _____ Date: _____
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The hosting researcher Name of the responsible person: Signature: _____ Date: _____

The receiving institution Name of the responsible person: Signature: _____ Date: _____
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Annex 2: Templates for documenting reflections

SECTION 1: Individual reflections of the visitor and the host

The questions provided are meant as “guiding questions”, it is not mandatory to answer them all nor should the respondent be limited by them.

Your name and Living Lab/WP/Task
Please, share in one sentence, what is the essence of learning you experienced with your visit?
Describe your learnings more broadly by considering e.g. the following questions. <ul style="list-style-type: none">- What was surprising? What kind of unexpected issues and experiences have you encountered?- What were meaningful experiences/moments considering your work/yourself? Why?- What kind of picture did you get from the visit's subject or theme?- What kind of new knowledge, skills, thoughts did you receive during the mobility? Why was it important to gain this new knowledge, how did you gain it? How do they differ from your previous thoughts, knowledge or skills?- Was there something that left you thinking?
Evaluate your learning by reflecting for example the following questions: <ul style="list-style-type: none">- Did the mobility meet your goals or expectations? (reflect back what they were)- What did go beyond?- Do you think that the visit somehow differed/changed your views, beliefs or values regarding our topic/Living Labs/methods/concepts? How?
Implications for the forthcoming activities/concrete outcomes for e.g. to yourself, the LL, and/or the project. <ul style="list-style-type: none">- How could you utilise or apply what you learned during the mobility later in your activities. How?- Are there any possibilities to upscale / replicate some of the new knowledge gained / practices experienced in the context of one's own organization/Living Lab?
Please, write down if you have other remarks.

SECTION 2: joint reflections (a dialogue)

Finally, you discuss jointly (visitor & host) and identify implications of the mobility. Here, you can use your notes from the individual reflection and share them with your pair/group. You may also recall back what you anticipated to achieve from the mobility and what you will take from the mobility for your future actions.

Your name and Living Lab/WP/Task
Please, share in one sentence, what is the essence of learning you experienced with your visit?
Describe your learnings more broadly by considering e.g. the following questions. <ul style="list-style-type: none">- What was surprising? What kind of unexpected issues and experiences have you encountered?- What were meaningful experiences/moments considering your work/yourself? Why?- What kind of picture did you get from the visit's subject or theme?- What kind of new knowledge, skills, thoughts did you receive during the mobility? Why was it important to gain this new knowledge, how did you gain it? How do they differ from your previous thoughts, knowledge or skills?- Was there something that left you thinking?
Evaluate your learning by reflecting for example the following questions: <ul style="list-style-type: none">- Did the mobility meet your goals or expectations? (reflect back what they were)- What did go beyond?- Do you think that the visit somehow differed/changed your views, beliefs or values regarding our topic/Living Labs/methods/concepts? How?
Implications for the forthcoming activities/concrete outcomes for e.g. yourself/individuals, the LL, and/or the project. <ul style="list-style-type: none">- How could you utilise or apply what you learned during the mobility later in your activities. How?- Are there any possibilities to upscale / replicate some of the new knowledge gained / practices experienced in the context of one's own organization/Living Lab?
Please, write down if you have other remarks.

Annex 3: Mobility Reports

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